

Doctor Alvaro Taveras Franco (EscID: 1560625)

Email: alvarotaveras73@gmail.com

Status : Submitted, submitted on 27/02/2026 01:58

Title : Association between obesity and arrhythmia risk in myocardial infarction with non-obstructive coronary arteries: a global analysis

Topic : 10.8 - Clinical

Category : Bedside

Option : No Options

Funding Acknowledgements :

Type of funding sources: None

Main funding source(s):

Project Code:

Agreement: 2

Doctor E. Crousett ⁽¹⁾, Doctor C. Tavaréz ⁽¹⁾, Doctor M. Almanzar ⁽¹⁾, Doctor A. Taveras Franco ⁽²⁾, Doctor L. Cruz ⁽²⁾

⁽¹⁾ Pontificia Universidad Católica Madre y Maestra, Santiago de los Caballeros, Dominican Republic, ⁽²⁾ Metropolitan Hospital of Santiago, Santiago de los Caballeros, Dominican Republic

Background: Arrhythmias are a common complication following myocardial infarction, yet their determinants in MINOCA remain poorly understood. Obesity is a known risk factor for atrial and ventricular arrhythmias in other populations.

Purpose: To evaluate the association between obesity and arrhythmia risk in patients with MINOCA.

Methods: Using the TriNetX global network, MINOCA patients were stratified by obesity status and matched 1:1 using propensity scores. The primary outcome was atrial fibrillation, with secondary outcomes including ventricular arrhythmias and all-cause mortality over 5 years.

Results: Among 516 matched patients, obesity was not associated with increased risk of atrial fibrillation (HR 1.22; 95% CI 0.41–3.62) or ventricular arrhythmias. Event rates were low, and confidence intervals were wide, limiting statistical power. Mortality rates were also similar between groups.

Conclusion: In this global cohort, obesity was not associated with increased arrhythmia risk in MINOCA patients. These findings suggest that arrhythmic risk in MINOCA may be driven by mechanisms distinct from those in obstructive coronary disease.